

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 64

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 64

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 64:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 64:1 לְמִנְצַחַת מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 64:1 Hear my voice, O God, in ^amy ¹complaint;</p>	<p>לְדָוָד : 2 שְׁמַע-אֱלֹהִים קוֹלִי בְשִׁיתִי מִפֶּתַח אוֹיֵב תִּצְרַר</p>
<p>^bPreserve my life from dread of the enemy.</p>	<p>תִּי : 3 תִּסְתִּירֵנִי מִסּוּד</p>
<p>² Hide me from the ^asecret counsel of evildoers,</p>	<p>מֵרָעִים מִרְגֵּשֶׁת פֶּעַלִּי אֶוֶן : 4</p>
<p>From the tumult of ^bthose who do iniquity,</p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר שָׁנְנוּ כִּתְרָב לְשׁוֹנָם</p>
<p>³ Who ^ahave sharpened their tongue like a sword.</p>	<p>דָּבְרוּ חֲצָצְמִים דְּבַר מָר : 5</p>
<p>They ^baimed bitter speech <i>as</i> their arrow,</p>	<p>לִירוֹת בְּמִסְתָּרִים תָּם פֶּתָאֵם יִרְהוּ וְלֹא יִירָאוּ : 6 יִתְזַקְוּ-</p>
<p>⁴ To ^ashoot ¹from concealment at the blameless;</p>	<p>לָמוּ וְדָבַר רָע יִסְפְּרוּ</p>
<p>Suddenly they shoot at him, and ^bdo not fear.</p>	<p>לְטִמּוֹן מוֹקְשִׁים אָמְרוּ מִי יִרְאֶה-לָמוּ : 7 יִתְפָּשׂוּ-עוֹלֹת</p>
<p>⁵ They ¹hold fast to themselves an evil purpose;</p>	<p>תִּמְנוּ חֲפֵשׂ מִחֲפֵשׂ וְקָרַב</p>
<p>They ²talk of ^alaying snares secretly;</p>	<p>אִישׁ וְלֵב עָמָק : 8 וַיִּלֹּם</p>
<p>They say, ^b“Who can see them?”</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים תֵּץ פֶּתְאוֹם הָיוּ</p>
<p>⁶ They ¹devise injustices, <i>saying</i>, “We are ²ready with a well-conceived plot”;</p>	<p>מִכּוֹתָם : 9 וַיִּכְשִׁילוּהוּ עַל־יָמוֹ</p>
<p>For the ^{3a}inward thought and the heart of a man are ⁴deep.</p>	<p>לְשׁוֹנָם יִתְנַדְּדוּ כָּל-רֹאֵה</p>
<p>Psa. 64:7 But ^aGod ¹will shoot at them with an arrow;</p>	<p>בָּם : 10 וַיִּירָאוּ כָּל-אֲדָמָה</p>
<p>Suddenly ²they will be wounded.</p>	<p>וַיִּגִּידוּ פֶּעַל אֱלֹהִים וּמַעֲשֵׂהוּ</p>
<p>⁸ So ¹they ²will ^amake him stumble; ^bTheir own tongue is against them; All who see them will ^cshake the head.</p>	<p>הַשְּׁכִילוֹ : 11 יִשְׁלַח צַדִּיק</p>

<p>⁹ Then all men ¹will ^afear, And they ²will ^bdeclare the work of God, And ³will consider ⁴what He has done.</p> <p>¹⁰ The righteous man will be ^aglad in the LORD and will ^btake refuge in Him; And all the upright in heart will glory.</p>	<p>בִּיהוָה וְתָסָה בּוֹ יִתְהַלְּלוּ כָּל-יִשְׂרָאֵל לֵב :</p>
---	--

References

Psalm 64:1

¹Or *concern*

^aPs 55:2

^aPs 140:1

Psalm 64:2

^aPs 56:6

^aPs 59:2

Psalm 64:3

^aPs 140:3

^aPs 58:7

Psalm 64:4

¹Lit *in*

^aPs 10:8; 11:2

^aPs 55:19

Psalm 64:5

¹Lit *make firm*

²Lit *tell of*

^aPs 140:5

^bJob 22:13; Ps 10:11

Psalm 64:6

¹Or *search out*

²Lit *complete*

³Or *inward part*

⁴Or *unsearchable*

^aPs 49:11

Psalm 64:7

¹Or *shot*

²Or *they were wounded*; lit *their wounds occurred*

^aPs 7:12, 13

Psalm 64:8

¹Or *they make their tongue a stumbling for themselves*

²Or *made*

^aPs 9:3

^aProv 12:13; 18:7

^aPs 22:7; 44:14; Jer 18:16; 48:27; Lam 2:15

Psalm 64:9

¹Or *feared*

²Or *declared*

³Or *considered*

⁴Lit *His work*

⁵Ps 40:3

⁶Jer 51:10

Psalm 64:10

⁷Job 22:19; Ps 32:11

⁸Ps 11:1; 25:20

Targum

Psa. 64:1 For praise, a psalm of David. ² Hear my voice, O God, in the time of my prayer; guard my life from the fear of the enemy. ³ You will hide me from the secret [council] of those who do evil, from the turmoil of those who practice deceit. ⁴ Who have sharpened their tongue as a sword, bent their bows, smeared their arrows with deadly and bitter poison. ⁵ To shoot in secret, without blame; suddenly they will shoot him and they will not fear. ⁶ They will strengthen themselves with an evil word; they will talk of hiding traps, saying, “Who sees them?” ⁷ They will search to find pretexts to destroy the pure, a search carried out in the body of a son of man, and the thoughts of a secret heart. ⁸ But God will shoot arrows at them suddenly; and they will tell of their wounds. ⁹ And their tongue will make them stumble; all who see them shall move aside. ¹⁰ And all the sons of men will be afraid, and tell of the work of the LORD God; and his works will be understood. ¹¹ The righteous man will rejoice in the LORD, and trust in his word, and all the upright of heart will boast.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm portrays the impudence of the word slander in all its dangerous connotations. It also says that slanders will eventually perish.

Superscript

David calls out to the Sefirah Netzach for victory over his enemies.

To the Sefirah Netzach, who grants victory, a psalm of David.

Verse one

שְׁמַע (sh'ma) means “hear”; however, in this context, it denotes inner growth of the mind and spirit.

O God hear my need to grow in mind and spirit; preserve my life from the fear of my foes.

Verses two, three, and four

David felt that only the LORD could protect him from a plot against him which was made in secret. Secrecy was considered a deadly weapon.

You alone can hide me from the secret counsel of evildoers, from the tumult of the workers of violence.

Who have sharpened their tongues like a sword and have aimed the bitter word as their arrow.

In order to strike the blameless man in secret places. They wish to strike him unaware, and they are not afraid.

Verse five

David's slanderers believed that the evil words they spoke are a strong weapon.

They think the evil word is strong; they lay hidden snares as they tell; they say, who would see them?

Verse six

A physical act of evil is traceable and can be investigated. However, a spoken word act of evil at times goes beyond recall unless it is recorded verbatim.

Let them investigate the iniquities; we shall be here no more when a search is done, for the man is within, and the heart is deep.

Verse seven

David's enemies felt safe slandering him. However, the LORD smote them with His arrows.

Then God smote them. A sudden arrow, their blows came to be.

Verses eight, nine, and ten

And they made their own tongue a stumbling block unto themselves; all those who look upon them feel moved.

And all men learned to fear, and they declared it as the work of God and understood His acts.

Let him who is righteous rejoice in God and take refuge in Him, and let all the upright in heart glory.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

O God hear my need to grow in mind and spirit; preserve my life from the fear of my foes.

You alone can hide me from the secret counsel of evildoers, from the tumult of the workers of violence.

Who have sharpened their tongues like a sword and have aimed the bitter word as their arrow.

In order to strike the blameless man in secret places. They wish to strike him unaware, and they are not afraid.

They think the evil word is strong; they lay hidden snares as they tell; they say, who would see them?

Let them investigate the iniquities; we shall be here no more when a search is done, for the man is within, and the heart is deep.

Let them investigate the iniquities; we shall be here no more when a search is done, for the man is within, and the heart is deep.

Then God smote them. A sudden arrow, their blows came to be.

Let him who is righteous rejoice in God and take refuge in Him, and let all the upright in heart glory.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

